

Defect-Induced Selectivity Modulation Using Copper Triazole Molecular Frameworks for Electrochemical CO₂ Reduction

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Metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) are considered promising electrocatalytic materials due to their adjustable coordination bonds between metal ions and organic ligands. The abundance of metal centers within MOFs offers potential active sites. However, the limited availability of adsorption sites in the case of fully coordinated metal ions might lead to insufficient electrocatalytic activity. The selectivity is tuned during the electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (eCO₂RR) using Cu-1H-1,2,3-triazole MOF from C₁ products to C₂₊ products by generating defects to enable a local increase in CO* coverage, thus improving eCO₂RR performance. The catalyst exhibits ≈78.4% of total Faradaic efficiency for C₂₊ products at –200 mA cm^{–2} current density in 1.0 M KOH as electrolyte.

the eCO₂RR.^[5] Various CO₂ reduction catalysts have been proposed, such as metal alloys, metal-oxides, metal-free nitrogen(N)-doped carbon catalysts, and metal–organic frameworks (MOFs) to tune the selectivity.^[6] MOFs are crystalline compounds consisting of metal centers or clusters coordinated to often rigid organic multi-functional molecules to form one, two, or 3D structures,^[7,8] which could be tuned for improved selectivity trends during eCO₂RR.^[6] However, if the active metal centers in a MOF are too far separated, the individual active catalytic sites often lead to the formation of exclusively C₁ products.^[9] Consequently, achieving the desired reduction products at high Faradaic

1. Introduction

The increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations has led to severe climate changes and has impeded progress toward a sustainable society.^[1] The electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction (eCO₂RR) is a promising approach for converting this greenhouse gas into valuable chemicals.^[2] Among the suitable metals, copper and copper-containing materials are uniquely capable of generating valuable C₂₊ products like ethylene and ethanol through the dimerization of adsorbed CO species.^[3,4] However, the ability of Cu to catalyze C–C coupling reactions, on the other hand, leads to the formation of up to 16 different C₁–C₃ products during

efficiency (FE), particularly C₂₊ hydrocarbons, remains challenging.^[10] It is widely understood that CO plays a pivotal role as an intermediate in the creation of multi-carbon products through either dimerization (CO–CO) or coupling (CO–COH) pathways.^[11] Both steps necessitate precursors, namely steady-state adsorbed CO (*CO) species, to be present on the surface in close proximity to each other and with high coverage.^[11] To achieve this, one can adjust the active sites and their density on the electrode surface following different strategies, namely by altering shapes and sizes, using dopants and employing mixed oxidation states of Cu⁺ and Cu⁰.^[12] These approaches typically enhance C₂₊ selectivity by reducing the energy barrier for CO* dimerization. Decreasing size and implementing defect-inducing strategies are pivotal in eCO₂RR and other electrochemical reactions. For example, Nam et al. have reported a strategy involving the regulation of Cu cluster formation within MOFs, which shifts CO₂ electroreduction toward multi-carbon products.^[13] Specifically, they promoted uncoordinated sites during the formation of Cu clusters by controlling the structure of the Cu dimer, which served as the precursor for Cu cluster formation. This was achieved by distorting the symmetric paddle-wheel Cu dimer secondary building block of HKUST-1 to an asymmetric motif through thermal treatment, thereby separating adjacent benzene tricarboxylate moieties. Applying this catalyst for electrochemical CO₂RR exhibited increased C₂₊ selectivity.^[13] Similarly, Tao et al. generated coordinatively unsaturated metal sites in ZIF-67 by

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Figure 1. Synthesis scheme for a) Cu-1H-1,2,3-triazole (Cu-triazole) and b) defect-Cu-1H-1,2,3-triazole (D-Cu-triazole) with their corresponding crystal structures.

employing dielectric barrier discharge plasma etching. Both density functional theory calculations and experimental measurements indicated a high catalytic activity of these sites for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER).^[14] Furthermore, Wang et al. discovered that introducing defects in HKUST-1 creates sites with higher adsorption energy pro-

viding simultaneously additional space for binding CO.^[15] This collective effect resulted in superior catalytic performance for low-temperature CO oxidation. These studies indicate that introducing defects in MOF might result in improved electrocatalytic activity and selectivity for a selected reaction.

Figure 2. Average FEs and iR-corrected potentials at different current densities for a) Cu-triazole and d) D-Cu-triazole, respectively. The uncompensated potential during chronopotentiometry is shown for b) Cu-triazole and e) D-Cu-triazole, respectively. Comparison of the FE for C₁+H₂ with the FE for C₂+ products for c) Cu-triazole and f) D-Cu-triazole, respectively.

Figure 3. a) p-XRD patterns of Cu-triazole, D-Cu-triazole, and the simulated pattern of Cu-triazole. b) Physical adsorption of CO₂ at 298 K. c) High-resolution XPS spectra of Cu 2p_{3/2} for Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole.

Another approach to generate open metal sites employs a competitive coordination strategy.^[16] Solvents and ligands bind to metal atoms to reach stable coordination numbers.^[17] Initially, all metal ions in the secondary building units of the synthesized MOF are in their fully coordinatively saturated state, typically with a coordination number of four (tetrahedral) or six (octahedral) for most 3d transition metals.^[17] To introduce these open metal sites into the metal secondary building units of MOFs, an initial labile terminal ligand, often a solvent molecule, must be removed from its coordinating metal atom.^[18] This process usually involves solvent exchange and subsequent solvent removal through activation.^[19,20]

The challenge lies in ensuring that the synthesis of open metal sites in MOFs by the general removal of coordinated solvent molecules proceeds without causing a collapse of the network structure. Wang et al. have proposed a defect engineering strategy to construct ligand defects in MOFs using a competitive coordination strategy.^[21] This approach can result in a significant exposure of open metal sites without compromising the structural integrity of MOFs, which could be advantageous for enhancing catalytic activity and modulate selectivity.

In this work, we studied the role of in situ generated defective Cu-1H-1,2,3-triazole MOF in tuning and increasing the selectivity from C₁ products to C₂₊ products during eCO₂RR. We discuss the dynamic reconstruction of the defect-based MOF during eCO₂RR which works as a pre-catalyst for enhanced selectivity toward C₂₊ products.

2. Results and Discussion

The Cu center in the Cu-triazole MOF is coordinated by six triazole ligands, and the assembly of such a small triazole ligand with Cu is the basis for its excellent stability. **Figure 1a** shows the synthesis scheme of the copper-triazole MOF (Cu-triazole) using Cu(OH)₂ in a (1:1) solution of ammonia and ethanol. **Figure 1b**

shows the synthesis scheme to generate defective copper-triazole (D-Cu-triazole) using Cu(NO₃)₂ and N,N-diethylformamide. The syntheses are described in detail in the supporting information.

After synthesis, Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole were studied for eCO₂RR. A flow-through model electrolyser cell was used, and the catalytic activities were evaluated in alkaline electrolyte (1M KOH). A catalyst-supported gas diffusion electrode (GDE) comprising a carbon paper with a hydrophobic microporous layer (Freudenberg, H23C6) was used as the working electrode (WE) with the constant flow of electrolyte through the catholyte compartment. Ni foam was used as counter electrode (CE), and Ag/AgCl/3 M KCl with a double junction filled with 1M KOH was used as a reference electrode (RE) **Figure S1a,b** (Supporting Information).

Galvanostatic measurements were conducted by applying constant current densities of −25, −50, −100, −150, −200, −250 and −300 mA cm^{−2}, respectively, for 422 s, followed by galvanostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at each current density value to determine the uncompensated electrolyte resistance for potential correction. All catalysts were mixed with polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE) to increase their hydrophobicity.^[22] The average catalytic performance of Cu-triazole at different current densities, along with iR-corrected potential and the uncompensated potential recorded during the experiment are shown in **Figure 2a,b**. Cu-triazole without defects exhibited higher Faradaic efficiencies (FE) for C₁ products and the parasitic hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). At −25 mA cm^{−2} (−0.65 V vs RHE), Cu-triazole exhibited a FE ≈41% for H₂, 31% for C₁ products, and 24.3% for C₂ products (**Figure 2c**). The highest FE for C₂₊ products (23.53%) was achieved at −150 mA cm^{−2}, whereas the highest FE for CH₄ (33.77%) was obtained at a current density of −200 mA cm^{−2}. The FE for H₂ exceeded 25% at each current density, and flooding of the GDE with electrolyte was observed beyond a current density of −200 mA cm^{−2}, most likely caused by electrowetting and modulation of the local pH value.

The predominant selectivity of the Cu-triazole MOF to form C₁ products together with a substantial competition by HER is supposedly due to the large Cu–Cu distance and bigger particle size which prevents C–C coupling of adjacently bound *CO similar to single-atom catalysts.^[23,24] Comparing eCO₂RR using Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole shows significant differences in product selectivity. In the case of D-Cu-triazole major eCO₂RR products were CO, ethylene, acetate and n-propanol (**Figure 2d,e**). With increasing current density from −25 mA cm^{−2} (−0.54 V vs RHE) to −300 mA cm^{−2} (−0.71 V vs RHE) the iR-compensated potential increases to a lower extent than in the case of Cu-triazole. The potential necessary to achieve a certain current density shifted toward lower overpotentials for D-Cu-triazole compared to Cu-triazole and carbon paper indicative for the modulation of the selectivity pathway. **Figure S3a,b** (Supporting Information) compare the Nyquist plots obtained from galvanostatic electrochemical impedance measurements of eCO₂RR with Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole as catalysts, respectively, used for determining the uncompensated electrolyte resistance.^[25] At −25 mA cm^{−2} high amounts of CO (FE of 55%) and ethylene (FE of 25%) were obtained, with the high initial formation of CO paving the way for C–C coupling to yield substantial amounts of C₂₊ products. The FE for H₂ remained at less than 10% at each current density. ≈94.5% of total FE toward eCO₂RR products was obtained at

Figure 4. a) TEM image, b) HR-TEM image, c) STEM image, d–h) STEM image with corresponding EDX elemental mapping of D-Cu-triazole.

-200 mA cm^{-2} with the highest FE for C_{2+} products of $\approx 78.4\%$ comprising almost 42% ethylene, 23% ethanol, 3% isopropanol, and 10% acetate (Figure 2d,f). This selectivity surpasses typical values for non-pyrolized MOFs. The high selectivity for C_{2+} products may be ascribed to a high coverage with CO^* .^[26]

As control, eCO_2RR measurements were also performed on bare carbon paper in absence of catalyst to exclude any parasitic product formation at the carbon paper itself (Figure S2a–c, Supporting Information). The major product was H_2 confirming the negligible contribution of the bare carbon paper toward eCO_2RR . A comparison of the catalysts concerning selectivity and iR-corrected potentials is provided in Tables S1 and S2 (Supporting Information), respectively. The FE for acetate at -300 mA cm^{-2} was $\approx 14\%$. Studies from electrochemical CO reduction to acetate suggest that acetate formation is favoured at high CO coverage and locally high pH when compared with ethylene and ethanol formation.^[26] Wei et al. reported a coverage-driven selectivity switch from ethylene to acetate in high-rate CO_2/CO electrolysis.^[27] With increasing CO pressure in the feed, the major product gradually switches from ethylene to acetate, attributed to the increased CO^* coverage and the high local pH.^[27] Hence, the formation of a significant amount of acetate also suggests that the catalyst exhibits high CO^* coverage during eCO_2RR which is an important prerequisite for C–C coupling concomitantly suppressing competitive H_2 formation. The overall FE for C_{2+} products reached $\approx 79\%$, and a FE of $\approx 94\%$ for all eCO_2RR products at a current density of -200 mA cm^{-2} was obtained.

To confirm the crystallographic structure and phase analysis of Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole, powder X-ray diffraction (p-XRD) was performed. The XRD patterns of the Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole samples are shown together with the calculated pattern of Cu-triazole (Figure 3a). Sharp and intense XRD reflections were obtained and the characteristic reflection near 8.78° corresponding to the (111) plane is in good agreement with the calculated XRD pattern.^[28] This suggests that the defects generated through the proposed in situ competitive coordination strategy using N,N-diethylformamide do not affect the structural integrity of the MOF framework. The nearest Cu–Cu distance of $\approx 3.77 \text{ \AA}$ (Figure S4, Supporting Information) for Cu-triazole favor higher amounts of C_1 products than C_{2+} products.^[24] Hence, we anticipated that Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole are ideal for studying defect-induced transformation modulating the adsorption sites and selectivity. CO_2 adsorption measurements were performed (Figure 3b), which reveal that D-Cu-triazole exhibits superior CO_2 adsorption capabilities compared to Cu-triazole. This increase in CO_2 uptake further supports the presence of open metal sites. To further confirm this hypotheses, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed in 20% O_2/He from room temperature to 700°C with a heating rate of $5^\circ \text{C min}^{-1}$ (Figure S5, Supporting Information).

Cu-triazole showed a weight loss at 305°C , while D-Cu-triazole already transformed at 260°C which is another indication for the presence of coordinated-unsaturated metal sites. It was shown that such unsaturated metal sites are prematurely oxidised sites and accelerate the collapse of the whole skeleton.^[21] The presence of such sites increase the local CO_2 concentration and the

Figure 5. a) FE of products during chronopotentiometry at a constant current density of -200 mA cm^{-2} . Post-electrolysis measurements: XRD patterns of b) D-Cu-triazole, bare carbon paper, and Cu nanoparticles deposited on the GDE. c) High-resolution Cu 2p XPS spectra, d) HR-TEM images, e) TEM image, f, g) STEM images with corresponding EDX elemental mapping of D-Cu-triazole after eCO_2RR at -200 mA cm^{-2} .

likelihood of interaction between reactants and active sites.^[29] This can lead to an improved activation of small molecules like CO_2 . There is a high chance of removing water molecules, if any, from the Cu atoms under the external stimulation of CO_2 .^[24] This suggests a direct role of open metal sites for electrochemical eCO_2RR . To gain further insights into the chemical states of Cu at the surface, the as-prepared Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole were further investigated using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

The survey spectra (Figure S6a,b, Supporting Information) confirm the presence of Cu, C, N, and O in both catalysts. The deconvolution of the high-resolution Cu $2p_{3/2}$ spectra (Figure 3c) reveals the presence of different Cu species, comprising Cu^+ likely from Cu_2O as well as Cu^{2+} . In addition to Cu^+ a broad satellite peak characteristic of Cu^{2+} is present in the Cu-triazole spectrum, which can be associated with $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$. Conversely, the D-Cu-triazole framework lacks the Cu^{2+} satellite peaks. Instead, it shows a dominant contribution by Cu^+ with a negligible contribution of Cu^{2+} . The higher abundance of Cu^+ species from unsaturated Cu centres in the D-Cu-triazole MOF further confirms the existence of the proposed ligand vacancy.^[21] Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) was performed to quantify the amount of Cu in the catalysts showing $\approx 26\%$ of Cu in D-Cu-triazole and 24.5% Cu in Cu-triazole Table S3 (Supporting Information).

The morphology and structural properties of the MOFs were investigated using field-emission scanning electron mi-

croscopy (FESEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging. Figure S7a,b (Supporting Information) show SEM images of D-Cu-triazole exhibiting a uniformly distributed particle-like morphology. TEM measurements (Figure 4a) show a similar morphology of the particles with particle sizes of 40–60 nm. However, HR-TEM does not show any crystalline phases (Figure 4b), which may be attributed to the sensitivity of the material to the high-intensive electron beams. Corresponding STEM images (Figure 4c,d) and the corresponding energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) elemental mapping (Figure 4e–h) confirm the presence of copper, oxygen, carbon, and nitrogen, respectively.

SEM images of the Cu-triazole MOF (Figure S8a–d, Supporting Information) display octahedral crystals with a large size of $\approx 1\text{--}5 \mu\text{m}$. Figure S9a,b (Supporting Information) show SEM images before and after EDX analysis of the Cu-triazole MOF, and the deformation confirms the material's sensitivity toward the high-intensity electron beam. Figure S9c–f shows the EDX elemental mapping of Cu-triazole, confirming the presence of copper, carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen, respectively. Generally, MOFs tend to form bulk crystals limiting their properties for electrocatalytic applications. Reducing the particle size is additionally favorable to increase the surface area and the number of exposed active sites with shorter diffusion pathways for CO_2 absorption and activation.^[30] Hence, both the particle size induced and open metal sites induced defects can play a crucial role in eCO_2RR .

Figure 6. a) In situ OLEMS chronopotentiometric measurements using a D-Cu-triazole-modified GDE at increasing current densities. b) Chronopotentiometry at prolonged electrolysis times at current densities of -25 mA cm^{-2} (2 min), -100 mA cm^{-2} (20 min), -200 mA cm^{-2} (40 min), respectively. c) Real-time OLEMS results for C_2H_4 , CH_4 , H_2 with increasing current densities. d) Real-time OLEMS results for C_2H_4 , CH_4 , H_2 for prolonged electrolysis times as in (b).

Operando Raman measurements with D-Cu-triazole-modified GDEs were performed to get insight into CO coverage and changes in local pH value. The experiments were performed using a custom-made cell (Figure S10, Supporting Information) in 0.1 M KHCO_3 as electrolyte by gradually increasing the reductive potential/current while continuously flowing CO_2 through the GDL side of the GDE. The comparison of the Raman spectra after introducing the electrolyte is shown in Figure S11a (Supporting Information). Several bands in the wavelength range of $1100\text{--}1300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were observed representing triazole ligand-related vibrations,^[31] which became more intense after introducing electrolyte. The impact of the cathodic current on the catalyst structure and the adsorbates is shown in Figure S11b (Supporting Information). Two broad bands of adsorbed HCO_3^- ($\approx 1366 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and H_2O (1600 cm^{-1}) become more pronounced with increasing cathodic currents (Figure S12, Supporting Information). Furthermore, we focused on adsorbed CO in the range between 1930 and 2200 cm^{-1} to estimate CO coverage. The normalised band is shown in Figure S13a (Supporting Information) and the corresponding heatmap in Figure S13b (Supporting Information). The band in the lower frequency region corresponds to bridge-adsorbed CO molecules ($\text{CO}_{\text{bridge}}$). The bands in the higher frequency region can be attributed to atop-adsorbed CO molecules (CO_{atop}).^[32–34] The coexistence of CO_{atop} and $\text{CO}_{\text{bridge}}$ species is believed to provide a low energy barrier for C–C coupling, suggesting favourable conditions for C_{2+} product formation. The rise in local pH together with the high CO coverage indicate a significant amount of acetate formation, which aligns with the obtained electrochemical results.

To further understand and confirm the behavior of D-Cu-triazole for electrochemical eCO_2RR , long-term measurements were performed at a current density of -200 mA cm^{-2} . Figure 5a shows a similar selectivity patterns for consecutive

measurements within 1 h electrolysis further confirmed through $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy (Figure S14, Supporting Information). A possible mechanism for the formation of the different eCO_2RR products is provided in Figure S15 (Supporting Information), while the potential during electrolysis is shown Figure S16 (Supporting Information). After 1 h chronopotentiometry at -200 mA cm^{-2} post-electrolysis characterization of the catalyst layer was performed. Figure 5b shows the post-electrolysis XRD pattern, suggesting reconstruction of the catalyst at the applied reductive potentials. Reduction of Cu to Cu^0 ^[35] is confirmed by the (111) and (200) reflections at 43.1° and 50.4° of the XRD pattern as well as by post-electrolysis XPS measurements (Figure 5c). Deconvolution of the Cu $2p$ signals confirms the formation of a higher amount of Cu^0 at the expense of Cu^{1+} and Cu^{2+} species. HR-TEM (Figure 5d) and TEM measurements suggest the formation of Cu nanoparticles (Figure 5e) showing the (111) and (200) planes with lattice spacings of 0.21 and 0.18 nm , respectively. Figure 5f–j shows the STEM images and the corresponding elemental EDS mappings confirming the presence of Cu, N, O, and C, respectively. Postmortem analysis at high potentials suggests that D-Cu-triazole is a pre-catalysts which transforms to the working catalyst during the reaction. To rule out any transformation caused by the harsh basic conditions in 1 M KOH , we performed 1 h and overnight chemical stability measurements in 1 M KOH for both the catalyst without applying any potential. The structural integrity was maintained for at least 1 h which was the duration of the measurements; however, additional reflections of CuO (ICDD card number 00-005-0661) after overnight exposure were observed (Figure S17, Supporting Information). This suggests that the active species are nitrogen-containing ligand-functionalized Cu nanoclusters formed by in situ electrochemical reduction rather than solely Cu^0 nanoparticles.

To gain an insight into the product formation in real time we performed on-line electrochemical mass spectrometry (OLEMS).^[36] A similar flow electrolyzer setup was used with D-Cu-triazole as catalyst, and similar potentials were recorded at the same predefined current densities (Figure 6a). Hydrogen ($m/z = 2$), methane ($m/z = 15$), and ethylene ($m/z = 26$) generated during eCO₂RR were simultaneously detected in real time (Figure 6c).

We observe a gradual increase in the signal for ethylene with each step of increased applied current up to -250 mA cm^{-2} . A further increase in the current density leads to a decrease of the ethylene signal, while the opposite trend is observed for hydrogen and methane. A subtle increase beyond -250 mA cm^{-2} was observed for both products most likely due to the comparatively high cathodic potential at current densities exceeding -250 mA cm^{-2} . Additionally, measurements with prolonged electrolysis times at different current densities, namely activation of the catalyst for 2 min at -25 mA cm^{-2} followed by 20 min at -100 mA cm^{-2} and 40 min at -200 mA cm^{-2} , were performed as shown in Figure 6b. At -100 mA cm^{-2} , both the hydrogen and methane signals were low and decreased over time, while the ethylene signal increased. At -200 mA cm^{-2} , the product selectivity was modulated with a gradually increasing formation of H₂ and decreasing ethylene production, suggesting that the catalyst was entirely transformed to Cu⁰ without any Cu⁺ species remaining preventing the formation of C₂₊ products (Figure 6d).^[37]

3. Conclusion

We demonstrate the performance of Cu-triazole and D-Cu-triazole MOFs modified GDEs for the eCO₂RR in model flow-through electrolyzers. Introducing open metal sites and reducing the particle size through a competitive coordination strategy with N,N-diethylformamide significantly enhances and alters the catalytic properties, resulting in an increased selectivity for C₂₊ products at high current densities for D-Cu-triazole. At a current density of -200 mA cm^{-2} , a FE of 78.4% for C₂₊ products was obtained. At -300 mA cm^{-2} a FE of $\approx 14\%$ for acetate was achieved. The structure-selectivity relationship during eCO₂RR was investigated using in situ Raman and OLEMS experiments, suggesting the transformation of the catalysts during eCO₂RR, forming nitrogen-containing functionalized Cu nanoclusters. By inducing defects in MOFs, we can successfully tweak and tune the selectivity for electrochemical CO₂RR.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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